

THEORETICAL BASIS OF FORMATION OF PERSON'S CREATIVE QUALITIES

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Abstract. *This article says that the systemic factor of the development of creativity of a person in higher educational institutions is the socialization of education, the first manifestations of creativity are various prohibitions in the growing, educational, educational environment of a person, social templates lead to a blocking (closing) of creative activity, and the opinion of pedagogical scientists.*

Keywords: *pedagogical technologies, creative approach, innovative skills, interactive methods, systematic approach, thinking, textbook, pedagogical technology.*

Introduction: The content, goals and tasks of education have expanded over time, and the forms and methods of the process have been improved. Currently, it is about integrated systems that ensure the full realization of the intended results in the directions of human activity. then, in recent years, pedagogical technology began to be used in such education. Pedagogical technology is based on the development of educational practices and is now a large-scale production of pedagogy and psychology. In pedagogical technology, different from various technologies in production fields, the clearly loaded material is the mental, spiritual, and moral qualities of the student (learner), and the teachers and educators have various influences on them in order to achieve certain goals.

The concept of pedagogical technology first appeared in the United States in the middle of the 20th century, and until the mid-1940s-50s, it was called "Educational technology" and this phrase was applied to teaching using technical means. In the 1950s and 1960s, programmed learning was considered, and in the 1970s, the phrase "pedagogical technology" was used, which meant the educational process that guaranteed the achievement of pre-planned and clearly defined goals. In 1979, Pedagogical Technology was defined as a complex, integrative process by the Association of Pedagogical Communications and Technologies of the USA, and since the beginning of the 80s, pedagogical technology was defined as the creation of computer and information technologies of education.

The main part: We are witness to the fact that all the developments of the "21st century intellectual century" i.e. "Intellectual age" or "Age towards the information society" are the result of the activities of the advanced creative people living in it, corresponding to the development of human society.

Usually, the following types of abilities are distinguished: intellectual (mental, thinking), artistic, organizational, communicative (communication), etc. The sum of various abilities that are highly developed is called talent.

Today, activities aimed at creativity, creativity, and innovation are understood as creative activities.

The word "creativity" is derived from the word "creativity" in English, meaning the ability of a person to be creative, and creativity is a level of talent, which characterizes the individual's readiness to create fundamentally new ideas far from the traditional or habitual thinking scheme,

as well as solving problems in a small way, creative abilities that are accepted as an independent factor of talent.

American scientist D. Wexler describes creativity as a type of thinking that requires a person to come up with several solutions to a problem or issue at once, and helps to understand the qualities of uniqueness and uniqueness in the essence of things and events, unlike templated, boring thinking.

To be a creative person, and in our example, to be a creative student means to have advantages in today's world, to stand out among other students, to be an interesting conversationalist compared to others, to overcome difficulties encountered in life in an unusual way.

The development of creativity in each student is individual. The systematic factor of creativity development is the socialization of education. The first manifestations of creativity are unique to each person. However, various prohibitions and social templates in the environment in which he hangs, is brought up, and learns lead to the blocking (closure) of creative activity. For the development of creativity in the student, it is necessary to free from psychological pressure and give a positive impulse.

The study of human creativity is one of the most important problems in psychology and pedagogy, and it is considered a very complex process, which requires constant research.

Thinking is carried out in concepts and imaginations, and the main form of thinking is thinking and reasoning. Thinking is a product of the development of society, but individual development of thinking, its uniqueness, depends on the uniqueness of the organism, the condition and functional capabilities of the brain. The individual characteristics of thinking are the breadth of thinking, independent thinking, speed of thinking, urgency and critical thinking, and experts consider these to be qualities of intelligence.

Broadness of thinking is the ability to fully cover the problem without losing sight of specific aspects. The depth of thinking is expressed in the ability to get to the heart of complex questions. The opposite quality to deep thinking is superficial thinking, where a person focuses on small things and misses the big picture. Independent thinking is characterized by a person's ability to pose new problems and find ways to solve them without resorting to the help of others.

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Thinking in a hurry - a person rushes to give a solution without thinking about the question, grabs some side, gives an insufficiently thought-out answer and reasoning. Slow thinking activity may depend on the type of nervous system, that is, its slow movement.

According to Eysenka's tariff: Speed of mental processes or speed of thought is the fundamental basis of intellectual differences between people.

In our opinion, the speed of thinking is the ability of a person to quickly and correctly assess a new situation or problem, adapt, understand and accept the right solution in a short time.

Summarizing the above, we can say that in modern psychology, the following several conditional classifications of thinking have been accepted and popularized according to different bases, they are: genesis of development; description of issues to be resolved; spread rate; level of novelty and originality; means of thinking; thinking functions, etc.

Thinking is a high form of human mental activity; the process of reflection of objective reality in the mind. Thinking is a tool for knowing the environment, social phenomena, reality, and also the main condition for human activity. It is a higher cognitive process that reflects reality more precisely than intuition, perception, and imagination.

Thinking is a special function of the human brain. Its neurophysiological basis is the interaction of the first and second signaling systems. In the process of thinking, thoughts, opinions, thoughts, assumptions, etc. are formed in a person and they are expressed in the mind of a person in the form of concepts, judgments, and conclusions. Thinking is closely related to language and speech. Thinking activity is manifested in the form of speech.

In the process of speech communication, the range of emotional observation of a person is not only expanded, but the acquired experience is also given to other people. Man is distinguished from other creatures by his thinking, speech and conscious behavior. He determines the reality of things and events that he reflects, perceives, imagines in the activity of thinking, determines whether the formed judgments, concepts, conclusions are true or not. Through Human Thinking, it summarizes reality and indirectly (indirectly), understands the most important connections, relationships, and characteristics between things and events. Consequently, a person has the ability to foresee the emergence, development and consequences of social events and phenomena based on certain laws, regulations and rules.

In the team, qualities of thinking such as critical view, self-criticism, assessment, self-examination, control, self-control, and group reasoning are formed. The perception of a person by a person is also inextricably linked with thinking. Creative works, discoveries, inventions, suggestions are products of thinking. Psychology also organizes the phylogenetic (period of the emergence of humanity), ontogenetic (throughout a person's life) historical aspects of thinking. Many complex problems of modern science require a deeper organization of logical processes in thinking.

In general, creativity is the creation of new, original ideas, a non-standard way of thinking, finding successful solutions to given problems. Creative thinking is a revolutionary thinking represents a constructive character. One of the important tasks of today is to develop goals and tasks that develop the creativity of students-young people who are interested in learning and creativity with their little minds, intelligence, and ingenuity.

Today, when science and technology are developing rapidly, the amount of scientific knowledge, understanding and imagination is increasing dramatically. This, on the one hand,

ensures its differentiation due to the development of new fields and branches of science and technology, and on the other hand, creates the process of integration between sciences.

In such conditions, the demands for highly qualified pedagogues are increasing, capable of educating a mature generation in the spirit of universal and national values that have been formed over the centuries, who have mastered the fundamentals of science, pedagogy and psychology methods, who have a high level of professional training, and who have the ability to keep modern pedagogical and information technologies in practice. and training of qualified creative pedagogues is required¹.

Currently, the wide range of pedagogical innovations in the educational process is a global trend of world development. Special attention is being paid to the systematic introduction of innovations in the field of education at the same time that the scope of pedagogical innovations is increasing and the modernization process is developing rapidly in the country. But despite the fact that many pedagogical innovations are being created, the level of implementation of pedagogical research on the implementation of new content, forms, methods and tools of teaching in educational processes cannot be considered sufficient.

In fact, in the introduction of the updated education system, it is an important requirement of today that every teacher should be able to regularly organize the news related to science and the education of the mature generation and keep them consistently in their work activities.

The formation and development of professional training of students of higher pedagogical educational institutions requires a systematic, comprehensive approach to this process. It is known that today all countries are trying to introduce as many innovations as possible to education. Today's news requires an organized, planned, public approach to them. News is the future for long-term investments. In order to arouse interest in innovation, to educate a person who strives to create new things, education should be enriched with innovations, and the atmosphere and spirit of creativity should prevail in it. Based on such relevance, today the independent field of pedagogy, pedagogical innovation, is rapidly developing.

The use of various educational technologies is effective in forming the knowledge of creative thinking of creative individuals.

In order to solve the problems faced by the educational system in the innovative processes taking place at the present time, independent and free-thinking persons who are able to evaluate the new information and evaluate the acquired knowledge by themselves are needed.

Therefore, the place and importance of modern teaching methods, interactive methods, innovative technologies in the educational process of educational institutions is incomparable. Pedagogical technology and their retention of knowledge and experience ensure that students are knowledgeable and proficient.

Innovation (English innovation) means innovation.

Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and teacher's and student's activities.

Interactive (Inter is to interact) means to interact or to be in conversation with someone. In other words, interactive methods of teaching are a special form of organization of knowledge and communicative activity, in which students are involved in the process of knowledge, they have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and understand. The role of the teacher in interactive lessons partially leads to directing the activity of students to achieve the goals of the lesson¹. Many pedagogues understand pedagogic technology as teaching techniques related to

information technology and necessary to stay in the teaching process, computer, distance learning or various technical tools. But this is a superficial approach to the issue, and most of the pedagogical technology the main basis depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher and the student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal.

The realization of the pedagogical goal and the achievement of a guaranteed result depend on the cooperative activity of the teacher and the student, the goal they set, the chosen content, style, form, tool, that is, technology. In order to achieve the result, it may be necessary to work with a computer, maybe you need a film or handouts. It all depends on the teacher's skills and the student's needs. Therefore, it is necessary and necessary for professors and teachers working in educational institutions to be able to use interactive methods and pedagogical technologies in their training in their fields.

Experts in the field have repeatedly noted that the use of pedagogical technology methods in the formation of a creative personality of divergent thinking has been widely effective. In this regard, we recommend the following pedagogic technology methods³ aimed at personal creativity.

Venn Diagram Graphic Organizer (GO)

Analytical approach to the subject in the students is aimed at forming the skills of reducing (synthesizing) the general essence of the subject on the basis of some parts. It is carried out according to a specific scheme based on the formation of small groups. A graphic organizer facilitates the comparative analysis of related theoretical knowledge, information, or evidence presented by learners. It is more effective to use it to organize final lessons on a specific section or chapters.

Case study technology

Case-study (in English, case method, study problem situation; situational analysis or analysis of problem situations) technology is an analysis of concrete, real or artificially created problem situations in students

serves to form the skills of finding the most optimal options. It trains learners to directly study and analyze any meaningful situation. At the core of the technology are elements that reflect the general essence of the process of solving a specific problem situation.

These are: forms of education, methods of education, means of education, methods and means of managing the educational process, methods and means of scientific research on problem solving, methods and means of gathering information, studying it, methods and means of scientific analysis, teacher and student methods and means of educational communication between them, educational results.

Conceptual Table GO

Trains learners to compare two or more aspects of an organized topic (issue or problem). When using it, students' ability to think logically on the subject and to present information systematically is developed.

During training, GO is used as follows:

1. The teacher determines the topic (problem) that needs to be solved
2. Students are introduced to the topic and the rules for using GO
3. Students are assigned to small groups
4. The groups perform the task assigned to them
5. The groups refer the solution to the judgment of the class (group) team
6. The solutions of the groups are discussed in the class (group) team

Fish skeleton GO

Forms the ability of learners to describe and solve the essence of a specific issue related to the subject. By studying it, students develop logical thinking, the basic concept that illuminates the essence of the topic, the skills of bringing data into a specific system and analyzing them.

Insert GO

Determining the students' (learners') possession of certain concepts on a new topic serves to form their analytical approach to the text.

Cluster GO

The cluster graphic organizer is a well-thought-out strategy that can be used in one-on-one and group sessions with learners. Clusters make it possible to generalize the proposed ideas and find connections between them.

Relationship method

Technology helps students to freely express their limited knowledge on the subject, to cover the content with the help of real-life examples.

The use of technology in the educational process creates the knowledge and skills of independent thinking, creative research, proving one's opinion and getting out of different situations based on the solution of specific issues related to the problem being organized, the causes of the origin of a certain process (reality, event), and finding ways to eliminate them. .

Technology has an educational character and helps learners to develop more positive qualities in themselves and to abandon negative ones.

Lily flower GO

Technology is one of the effective means of solving didactic problems and has the appearance of a lily flower. The base consists of nine petals (squares, rectangles or circles) attached to it using this method.

which allows to illuminate the problem and its content
private issues are resolved.

Plan method

The method serves to form the skills of students to develop a plan for organizing pedagogical activities based on theoretical knowledge of a specific section or chapters. Keep it

It requires students to have the ability to carefully summarize the content of the topic being organized, summarize the main ideas, and put it into a certain system.

The method allows students to organize their activities in pairs, groups and teams. It is more effective to keep it in the organization of spiritual and educational activities, conducting volunteer activities, organizing pedagogical practice.

Usually, in the development of the plan, the pedagogical situation, age, pedagogical and psychological characteristics of the learners, the burning of spiritual and educational work, the content and the ability to achieve efficiency are taken into account.

T-table GO

The graphic organizer is used for the purpose of comparing the basic concepts with each other, for the purpose of detailing the specific aspect of the topic or issue organized on the basis of several main signs. In many cases, the graphic organizer is used in order to compare the advantages or disadvantages, effectiveness or ineffectiveness, importance for today and the future of several cases covered in the content of the topic.

SWOT analysis strategy

The strategy serves to illuminate the main cause aspect of the problem. Learners illuminate the essence of problems relevant to the content of the subject by thoroughly studying them, search for the factors that cause them, and find opportunities to solve them.

With its help, the following aspect of the problem is analyzed:

S-Strength (pillar) aspects (covering the advantages of the problem being solved)

W-Weak (weak) aspects (studying the influence of internal factors on the activities organized to achieve the goal)

O- Identifying opportunities (looking for the most optimal ways to solve certain tasks)

T- Study of the threat (organization to achieve the goal
determining the impact of external factors on actions)

Strategy of FSMU

The graphic organizer serves to form students' ability to independently express their opinions on the subject being organized, prove their personal opinions (justify them with examples), and argue.

Countermeasure strategy

Based on the analysis and synthesis of the knowledge reduced by the students, the strategy allows to divide the main and secondary concepts that are important in explaining the topic into groups.

Decision tree (decision-making) strategy

The strategy is a technical approach aimed at reducing complex topics related to the foundations of certain science, coming to certain conclusions based on a comprehensive and careful analysis of certain issues, and finding the most appropriate and correct one among the several conclusions expressed about the problem. It serves to re-analyze the decisions made in previous situations, to understand them perfectly.

Conclusion: In order to make a rational decision (come to a conclusion) about the problem being organized, the application of the strategy in education creates an opportunity to analyze each option presented by the students, to determine the acceptable and unacceptable aspects. The main aspects of pedagogical technology were created for the purpose of improving the current traditional education in various directions and are currently developing. It is very important for teachers of different subjects to choose the most convenient empirical, cognitive, heuristic, creative, inversion, integrative, adaptive, inclusive and other directions of the most convenient pedagogical technologies in accordance with the main features of each academic subject, the composition of its content, and the ratio of practical and theoretical parts.

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